

The Rajamouli Cinema: A Reflection of Indian Rasa Theory & Aesthetics

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Abstract:

After the re-release of the cult classic, the *Baahubali* series movie as a single movie with the title *Baahubali: the Epic*, it is pertinent to delve into the craft of its director, S.S. Rajamouli who is now an all-time great filmmaker representing the 21st century Indian cinema, which amalgamates fantasy, myth-making and uses technical finesse. His next project, *Varanasi* which he termed as his most ambitious one is a globe-trotter and a time-trotter, another genre defining moment for Indian Cinema.

Keywords: Cinema, India, Rajamouli, Rasa Theory, Indian Aesthetics

Introduction

The name SS Rajamouli is synonymous with creating a moment of 'wonder and awe', in the filmmaker's cinematic choices, for the viewers. The mainstay of the internationally acclaimed director, according to the people, is his uncanny ability to integrate art and commercial aspects of cinema, by infusing emotions into the audience and making them slip into a world of larger-than-life and make it believable.

The projection and positioning of the typical 'hero', or to use the Indian theory of aesthetics, the '*Nayaka*' the 'Rajamouli way', is a total reflection of our Indian aesthetic theory of *Rasa* of Sage Bharatha, as enumerated in his *Natyasastra* the treatise on fine arts like drama and dance. An aspect that Bharatha illustrates as a main aspect of an exemplary artist, is to 'transfer the emotions felt by the actor to the audience' and make it 'their own emotion for the entire duration of the performance, be it dance, music or play (1). This aspect Abhinavagupta, the commentator of *Natyasastra* calls '*Sadharanikarana*' or the process of normalising the emotion in the psyche of the audience, for the moment of the performance. (2). It is a calculated endeavour of the performer to create a sense of wonderment and empathy in the mind of audience when an act is performed. Creating the 'enjoyment of *Rasa*' or *Rasa Asvadana* (tasting the emotion personally), is the acme of any art be it visual or aural art.

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Rajamouli: Master of Emotions (Rasas)

Rajamouli has perfected this art of goading his audience into his world of *Adbhuta Rasa*, to use another Bharata's term to convey the emotion of wonder in his Rasa theory. We observe that Rajamouli's strength is to create moments of empathy in the audience and make them feel for the characters they are 'seeing' on the screen.

How else you explain the wonder one experienced when Bheem (Junior NTR) hatched a masterstroke of hustling the wild animals in a truck and unleashing them in the British residency in *RRR* (2022)? Or how can one explain the emotion when one feels for the character of Amarendra Baahubali (played by a superb Prabhas), who holds the royal insignia to the usurper of his throne, Bhallaladeva (Rana) in the coronation scene in *Baahubali: The Beginning* (2015)?

The emotions are heightened by use of apt background music and Sanskrit verses by Sivasaskthi Dutta (father of composer MM Keeravani and a Sanskrit-Telugu scholar who contributes to rousing lyrics to heighten Rajamouli's heroes in his films). Observe the adventure of Mahendra Bahubali to climb up the waterfall, the background score soars to heights (as if to point out to the heights he scales) with the refrain in Sanskrit "*Dheevera*" which literally means 'the best among courageous and valorous' and the song continues to extol the qualities of the hero. So, the use of cultural heritage symbols like language, mythological overtones and panes of praise to gods become a part of the Rajamouli universe of wonderment.

Similarly the title song of *Chatrapathi* (2005), a mass movie which draws upon the legend of Maharaja Sivaji who became the beacon light for his men in Mughal India and juxtaposes to the hero character Sivaji (Prabhas in a tailor-made role for him as the angry young man), also is in Sanskrit and uses tongue twisting Sanskrit lyrics, '*Agniskhalana..*' (the one oozing with fiery demeanour etc) to heighten the emotion of his valour.

We now come to the point where we can clearly see the tradition from which Rajamouli comes from. Rajamouli belongs to the world of Telugu cinema, which never failed to create an 'emotion' in its audience. The talkie era in Telugu began with the stories of fables from Indian mythology and folklore, before drifting into more of social genres (The first 'talkie' in Telugu *Bhakta Prahlada* (1931) was a fable form the *Bhagavatha* which told the story of a devotee of Vishnu and is a story of 'good winning over evil'. But it

is interesting that the genres of mainstream entertainment including mythological, folklore, social and historical were fairly represented in Telugu cinema till as late as early 2000s (3).

The master of margining social, mythological and folklore genres in Telugu was undoubtedly K.V.Reddy (1912-1972) who made the timeless classic of the Telugus, *Mayabazar* (1957), a mythological genre movie which took its plot from a popular play with some characters from *Mahabharatha* and some fictitious characters created by the team *Mayabazar*. This tradition of merging the 'seemingly opposite' genres into a tapestry of entertainment genre from K.V.Reddy which continued till films like *Bhairava Dweepam* (1994) a folklore directed by the legendary auteur Singeetam Srinivasa Rao (1931-).

Rajamouli inherited this tradition and made blockbusters with use of technology and his understanding of framing. Observe the socio-fantasy *Yamadonga* (2007) of Rajamouli where the hero traverses the mortal world and meets the Hindu god of Death, Yama and challenges his judgements. It is a classic example of 'fusing the binaries of social and mythological genre' into a successful commercial model of 'good wins over evil'.

The *Rasas* (emotions) of *Vira* and *Adbhuta* play an important role in Rajamouli's cinema, the interval points of his films draw a long episode of heightened evil and the second half depicts the way the hero wins over the evil.

Take the role of the fantastic *Eega* (2012) where a man reincarnates as a fly and takes revenge over the villain. The film includes the model of infusing mythical, folklore and social aspects of storyline. The craft of Rajamouli lies in 'transferring these emotions' the '*Sadharanikarana*' of emotions to his audience with a sense of wonderment. Hence, he is a personification of Indian aesthetics and the KV Reddy model of fusing genres into one and creating a 'wonderful' (pun intended) universe of *Adbhuta* rasa.

The reincarnation theme in *Magadheera* (2009) too makes this successful jugglery of creating a fable of Bhairava (Ram Charan) who loses his ladylove and reincarnates and gets his girl by taking revenge on his previous birth detractors. Even in making a rugby -based sports drama *Sye* (2004) perhaps the FIRST non-cricket sports drama in India, Rajamouli introduces a villain who is on the lines of Kamsa the villain of *Bhagavatha* who wants to kill Krishna, but eventually is killed by him.

These characterisations of Rajamouli cannot be dismissed as mere coincidences, but are deeply personal choices of a filmmaker who is firmly 'rooted in the culture of Telugu cinema' who contemporises the epoch-making genres which contributed to the richness of Telugu mainstream cinema.

In entirety, Rajamouli is a rare confluence of audacity, perseverance, smart craft and a story telling genius of India, who is now spreading the wings of his into the skies of foreign lands quite valorously like his heroes To take the epithet that Karan Johar gave him, Rajamouli is the 'Greatest Showman of 21st century Indian Cinema'(4).

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